

EFFECT OF EXCIPIENTS ON THE QUALITY OF PELLETS AND MULTIPARTICULATE TABLETS

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Abstract. Research has been carried out to assess the impact of excipients on the quality of doxycycline hydrochloride pellets with glucosamine hydrochloride and multiparticulate tablets based on them.

Keywords: multiparticulate tablets, excipients, qualitative parameters

The relevance of the topic. The modern type of dosage form is multiparticulate tablets, which contain pellets of the active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) — particles of a regular spherical shape with a diameter of 0.5-1.5 mm. Pellets allow not to create high concentrations of medicinal substances in one place of the gastrointestinal tract, contribute to increased bioavailability. They can be covered with a shell to ensure the release of API in a certain area of the gastrointestinal tract or to protect against environmental factors. Pellets must have optimal pharmaco-technological properties required for applying a quality coating, such as appropriate bulk volume, compaction and friction force to avoid damage during the coating process; approximately spherical shape to obtain good flowability and rotation in coating equipment, appropriate size, size distribution and density [1, 2].

Doxycycline is a broad-spectrum antibiotic that has proven itself in the treatment of various diseases. However, the use of doxycycline is associated with frequent manifestations of side effects from the body, such as nausea and esophageal ulcers, if the capsules for some reason do not reach the stomach and remain in the esophagus.

It has been proven by prof. I.A. Zupanets and Y.F. Grintsov, PhD, with coauthors at the National University of pharmacy that the antimicrobial activity of doxycycline hydrochloride increases, and the toxicity decreases when combining it with glucosamine hydrochloride in a ratio of 1:1 [3, 4]. Therefore, the combination of doxycycline and glucosamine is promising for the creation of a new drug based on it for the treatment of infectious diseases.

Due to some irritating effects of doxycycline hydrochloride on the stomach, it was proposed to release doxycycline and glucosamine hydrochloride from the dosage form in the intestine for good tolerability of the drug.

Aim. The purpose of our work was to study the effect of excipients on the quality of multiparticulate tablets with doxycycline hydrochloride and glucosamine hydrochloride.

Research methods. Technological properties and qualitative parameters of pellets and tablets were determined by the generally accepted methods.

Main results. To obtain pellets of doxycycline hydrochloride and glucosamine hydrochloride, we used the method of layering the powder on the initial spherical cores in a rotating coating pan.

Doxycycline hydrochloride is a finely dispersed crystalline powder with particles of anisometric shape in the form of small prisms and their shapeless fragments. The powder consists of two fractions: the first fraction has particles with a length of 20-70 μm and a width of 4-10 μm ; the average particle size of the second fraction is 2-15 μm . The substances of doxycycline hydrochloride and glucosamine hydrochloride were previously ground and sieved through a sieve with a diameter of 5 μm , and then each substance was mixed with excipients.

The resulting pellets were coated with an enteric coating using polymethacrylate Eudragit L 100 from Röhm Pharma (Germany), which dissolves at a pH above 5.5 and has high moisture-protective properties during storage. pH 5.5 corresponds to the upper part of the intestine, where the absorption of active substances begins. In our case, it is advisable to use an ethanolic solution of polymethacrylate, rather than aqueous dispersions of polymers, due to the possible

hydrolysis of glucosamine hydrochloride. In addition, the temperature of film formation of aqueous dispersions is quite significant (about 85 °C), which excludes their use for such a thermolabile substance as doxycycline hydrochloride.

The optimal amount of dry coating per 10 g of pellets is 1.2%, which allows you to obtain a coating that is stable in the gastric environment (0.1 M HCl solution) for 2.0 hours and soluble in the intestines for 30-35 minutes.

The initial cores were poured into the coating pan, and then a sprayed binder solution was periodically added through a nozzle until the core layer became wet and sticky, and then the sifted active ingredient powders with glidants were added until the layer became dry. The powder layering process was well with the specified amount of binder solution and powder. Feeding an excess of powder led to high losses of medicinal substances with removed air, solidification of the powder on the walls of the pan, and the formation of non-nucleated agglomerates of particles of medicinal substances of different sizes. On the other hand, an excess of binding liquid led to overwetting of the layer, which caused the formation of sticky agglomerates between the pellets and the walls of the pan. It is also determined that the speed of rotation of the pan significantly affects this process. The low speed of rotation (about 10 rpm) of the pan caused the accumulation of nuclei, while the speed of rotation of 20 rpm made it possible to apply the powder on the surface of the nuclei in the necessary manner without the formation of agglomerates. During the pelletization process, the temperature of the air supplied to the pan was maintained at $(29 \pm 1)^\circ\text{C}$. At the end of the process, each series was subjected to drying. A plasticizer and a pigment were introduced into the film-forming system from an organic solution.

The excipient layer of pellets showed significance in improvement of the compressibility of coated pellets and maintaining the medicine release properties of coated pellets after tableting. It provided a rational way to circumvent the segregation problems associated with mixing of coated pellets and excipients for compression, and could absorb the compression force to protect against film rupture. It is known that macrogol 4000 can be used as plasticizer for an alcohol solution of Eudragit L 100. The amount of macrogol 4000 was determined experimentally. It amounted to 9% in terms of dry components of the coating. In order to more evenly distribute the components in the mass of the coating, medical talc was added to the composition.

The quality and effectiveness of the coating on the pellets depends on the technological modes of applying the film solution, the viscosity of the film-forming solution, their flawability, the amount of suspended solid components, the smoothness and adhesive properties of the particle surface.

Conclusions. Thus, the effect of excipients on the quality of doxycycline hydrochloride pellets and multiparticulate tablets based on them with glucosamine hydrochloride has been carried out. The influence of the following parameters on the process of obtaining quality pellets of doxycycline hydrochloride and glucosamine hydrochloride was established: the size of the initial nuclei; required fineness of powders, their flawability and wettability; type of binding solution and its concentration; the speed of feeding the sprayed solution and powder; the presence of moisture, pan rotation speed; the location of the spray nozzle and the degree of spraying; the temperature of the supplied air, the temperature of the layer and the size of the pellets.

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